

D7.4: Communication and Dissemination Plan (b)

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SUMMARY SHEET

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List of Participants

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2		FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	Spain
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4		FOM TECHNOLOGIES A/S	FOM	Denmark
5		DEEP BLUE SRL	DBL	Italy
6		NETZSCH FEINMAHLTECHNIK GMBH	NFT	Germany
7		RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN	RWTH AACHEN	Germany
8		SINTEF AS	SINTEF	Norway
8a		SINTEF OCEAN AS	SINTEF- OCEAN	Norway
9		POMEGA ENERJİ DEPOLAMA TEKNOLOJİLERİ ANONİM ŞİRKETİ	POMEGA	Turkey
10		CEGASA ENERGIA S.L.U.	CEGASA	Spain
11		LECLANCHÉ GMBH	LEC	Germany

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	Extended
CMS	Content management system
DMS	Document management system
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Index
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
WPL	Work Package Leader
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

This deliverable D7.4 – *Communication and Dissemination Plan (b)* contains the BATMACHINE plan for dissemination and communication strategy, tools and methods, advisory board terms of reference and guidelines, updated at M18 (November 2024) of the project.

In this deliverable, the WP7 activities related to Dissemination and Communication are listed and described in terms of performance, in addition to comparing the actual status of the WP/ KPIs to the KPI objectives defined in D7.1 – *Communication and Dissemination Plan (a)*.

This deliverable D7.4 will be followed by D7.6, the final report on the Communication and Dissemination activities, due in M42, which will feature all the BATMACHINE Communication and Dissemination activities and efforts.

Partners' Contributions

<i>Partner institution</i>	<i>Sections</i>	<i>Description of the contribution</i>
DBL	All	First draft for partners' review
All partners	All	Contribution to report
VUB	All	Final comments
DBL	All	Final draft
VUB	All	Final check and submission

Project Overview

The BATMACHINE project is centred on strengthening Europe's battery cell industrial manufacturing value chain by developing new battery cell manufacturing machinery. This will be done while giving priority to minimising the energy for cell production, enhancing plant efficiency rates, and integrating intelligent control processes to reduce scrap.

The project will develop and implement an optimised and energy-efficient process chain considering:

- Slurry mixing (automated modular process set-up including monitoring techniques).
- Exclusive slot-die coating and drying novel machinery (with one side coating, a coating speed of 1m/min up to 20m/min and a web-width of 300 mm).
- A calendaring tool to be integrated in a battery manufacturer for process optimisation.

Moreover, intelligent control processes and Industry 4.0 will be intensively integrated through the creation of a collaborative and FAIR data space for battery production. Digital interfaces between battery manufacturing equipment, control system, and engineers will be developed with the aim of building universal digitalisation tools to enhance the battery production and create a battery passport. The environmental and economic impact of different machinery, production line configurations and factory designs will be deeply studied to reduce the cost and energy consumption of manufacturing processes.

1. Communication and Dissemination Overview and Strategy

Communication and dissemination activities represent a key part of the project. These activities are to convey information about the project, to promote the achievements to all the potential interested parties, to raise awareness across multiple communication channels, ensuring publication and promotion towards different stakeholders to achieve the largest possible impact for BATMACHINE results.

In particular, the BATMACHINE Communication and Dissemination strategy focuses on highlighting key aspects and benefits of BATMACHINE's new technologies, targeting specific stakeholders, and emphasising the project's objectives.

For full and detailed information about the BATMACHINE Communication and Dissemination strategy, please refer to [D7.1 – Communication and Dissemination plan \(a\)](#).

1.1. Communication and Dissemination Goals

The BATMACHINE project aims to strengthen Europe's battery cell industrial manufacturing value chain by developing new battery cell manufacturing machinery that would make production more efficient, sustainable and with reduced scrap. By focusing on key areas, the project wants to contribute to the advancement of battery technology and support the transition towards a more sustainable future.

The project adopts a scientific approach, leveraging a consortium of diverse partners to handle the technical aspects. The key role of WP7 is to find the strategic ways to process the scientific and technical results into comprehensible and easy to elaborate information for the wider stakeholders' community, communicate project milestones and outcomes to ensure their uptake (dissemination) and impact on the long term.

Depending on the phase of the project and on the stakeholders expected involvement, the communication and dissemination activities' aim is to reach:

- **Awareness** of BATMACHINE activities, providing all the information about the project, promoting its achievements to all interested parties.
- **Understanding**, by transferring key messages to specific stakeholders and enhancing their comprehension of BATMACHINE's outcomes.
- **Engagement**, by promoting effective materials and information that will facilitate the interaction of stakeholders' communities.

1.2. Target Audience

BATMACHINE is targeting a variety of stakeholders able to uptake the solutions and outputs developed in the project. They have been categorised under seven main clusters:

1. **T1 - Battery process equipment companies:** EU and international battery manufacturing companies involved in battery production, as BATMACHINE will develop a new way of producing batteries that aims to be more efficient, sustainable, and digitalised.

2. **T2 - Industrial-scale cell manufacturing**, engaged in the development, marketability, and sale of environmentally friendly and digital battery manufacturing for better, cheaper, cleaner, and safer battery cells.
3. **T3 - Material, energy, and other supply chain sectors.**
4. **T4 - Decision and Policy Makers:** European and National levels (i.e., European Commission, Industrial associations, Stakeholder communities and networks, such as the [LiPlanet](#), [BatteriesEurope](#), [BEPA](#)). The project will establish dedicated communication channels and products to communicate information and ideas early and often. This ensures that policymakers are aware and informed about the adopted methodologies and results, gaining their full endorsement regarding innovative regulations.
5. **T5: Standardisation Bodies.**
6. **T6 - Scientific and Academic Communities:** Universities, EU RTD projects, BATTERY 2030+ large scale initiative, academia and research organisations, educational institutions. The project will establish an Advisory Board to ensure the scientific soundness of the proposed solutions methodologies.
7. **T7 - Educated Workforce:** European skilled workforce (e.g. technicians, engineers, that show an interest to work with developed machinery, blue-collar and white-collar employees in the battery industry), students graduating from European universities.
8. **T8 - Interested general public**, potential consumers of final products using more sustainable batteries.

The wide range of different audiences outlined above is requiring different communication and dissemination strategies, using different styles, languages, content types and levels of detail for each specific cluster.

2. Communication Means and Activities

The communication of the BATMACHINE project is a collaborative activity managed by DBL and supported by the whole consortium, to ensure an effective diffusion of information. Partners have a central role in identifying the different target audiences and domain-specific channels in their countries. Tailored messages enhance the level of engagement, depending on the type of the target audience. Moreover, all listed communication means are easily updated throughout the duration of the project, and the contents and tone of messages are adaptable and tailored when needed and additional communication goals to the specific activity are implemented if necessary.

The communication and networking actions are divided into:

- **Communication means:** brochures, flyers, newsletters, videos, and all multimedia products that can be easily sent, printed, or digitally exchanged. All these materials will also be uploaded as digital resources on the project website and can be downloaded for free.
- **Dissemination means:** Scientific papers, policy briefs, white papers, reports, and all other means that are specifically developed to promote project results either digitally or during workshops, conferences, and events.
- **Communication and dissemination channels:** all the available channels such as website, social networks and other online platforms or tools for official

communication and dissemination (e.g., newsletter, survey tools, scientific articles platforms, video hosting platforms).

- **Communication and dissemination activities:** live events, workshops, conferences organised by the project or by consortium members promoting the project objectives and results.
- **Participation to relevant external events:** BATMACHINE will keep updated on the events organised by relevant actors active in the field of battery manufacturing, energy, and sustainability. For instance, the project will participate in CINEA, BATT4EU, and European Battery Alliance (EBA) events, as well as the events, workshops and activities organised by sister projects.

For more detailed information on the BATMACHINE Brand Identity, Communication and Dissemination package, please refer to D7.1 – *Communication and Dissemination Plan (a)*.

2.1. Branded Graphic Identity and Project Multimedia tools

2.1.1. New concept image and infographics

BATMACHINE produced a new version of the concept image (see Figure 1), which illustrates the technical WPs of the project. In this second version of the Concept Image, the aims was to show in a simple and graphically clear way what each of the technical WPs is dealing with.

Figure 1: BATMACHINE 2nd Concept Image illustrating the interaction of the technical WPs

Furthermore, updated versions of the BATMACHINE Timeline have been created to showcase the progress of the project. Below, Figure 2 and Figure 3 showcase such updated timelines, respectively at M18 and M42 of the project.

Figure 2: BATMACHINE Timeline (updated at M18)

Figure 3: BATMACHINE Timeline (updated at M42)

2.1.2. Brochures and Flyers

To facilitate communication and dissemination during public events, BATMACHINE produced printed and digital flyers and brochures as outreach materials. These materials served to present the project's goals, outcomes, and findings. The structure of the brochures is tailored to the specific type of conference and communication objective, allowing for flexibility in content and style. The textual content of the brochures is determined in advance through collaboration with the partner(s) attending the conference. Furthermore, to ensure accessibility and timeliness, the brochures and flyers are regularly updated and made available for download on the project's website.

BATMACHINE produced one flyer featuring the project overview, its objectives, partners and points of contact. The Overview flyer was produced in two versions: a [classic flyer](#) and a [trifold, "battery-like" brochure](#). The horizontal brochure can hold more information and graphic content than the classic flyer, thus it will be used for specific occasions, such as showcases of BATMACHINE products. The BATMACHINE flyer and brochure were brought by the partners in relevant events where they presented the project and/or held a stand at the venue.

Both flyer and horizontal brochure are available for viewing and download on the project website.

Figure 4: BATMACHINE flyer (both sides)

Figure 5: BATMACHINE horizontal brochure (both sides)

2.1.3. Roll-up and Posters

BATMACHINE has created templates for roll-up and project poster to provide more extensive and detailed information. Building upon the content used in the brochures, these materials aim to inform and engage a wider audience. The roll-up and project poster feature QR codes that link to additional online resources, including the website, videos, and other relevant information.

The roll-up and posters are professionally printed and prominently displayed during public project events, conferences, and in person workshops. They serve as visual aids to enhance the project's visibility and facilitate access to supplementary materials for interested individuals.

Figure 6: BATMACHINE Rollup (left) at the LOLABAT Project Final Conference (Sept.2024)

2.1.4. Presentations

To effectively engage audiences during conferences, workshops, events, and internal meetings, BATMACHINE produces well-structured presentations, according to the visual identity of the project. The presentations intended for external events focus on graphical elements rather than excessive textual information to captivate the target audience. They prominently feature essential project references, including links to the project website, social media pages, and contact information. These presentations are stored in dedicated repositories and made readily accessible on the website for free download, when possible.

All project partners contribute to creating and organising the presentation contents, with support from DBL, which provides guidelines and suggestions for maintaining a cohesive visual identity, as well as support in the design of infographics, images and visual elements. The BATMACHINE Project Overview presentation is [available on the project website](#).

2.1.5. Videos

A project video will be delivered to outline the main achievements and the rules/regulations proposed by the project. Videos are well-suited to deliver information in a very effective and immediate way and are often considered one of the best options to raise awareness.

BATMACHINE will produce a project video between M25 and M29 depending on the status of advancement of machinery innovations. The video will be either in motion graphics or using recorded materials to showcase its main achievements and results. This video will represent the conclusion of the entire project, a summary of BATMACHINE's overall activities.

DBL's YouTube channel will be used to publish the video, distributed through various channels (e.g., social networks, project, and partners' websites) and, whenever possible, displayed during public events or conferences.

2.2. Communication Channels and Activities

2.2.1. Website and News

The [BATMACHINE website](#) provides a comprehensive overview of project objectives, planned activities and results. It also introduces the consortium, offers references to linked projects and activities within the BATTERY 2030+ framework, and provides an overview of news, articles, and tools.

Project Overview & Main Purpose

To meet future battery demand, the battery manufacturing sector must become **greener and more cost-effective**. This can be achieved by **reducing the energy consumption** during production and **by incorporating digital tools** to enhance the entire process.

BATMACHINE project is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative that aims to **boost Europe's sustainable industrial battery cell manufacturing value chain** by developing an optimised machinery with

Figure 7: BATMACHINE website Homepage

The website is constantly updated and represents the main dissemination activity channel: news, progress, events, upcoming workshops and any other announcement is issued via its news section. It also serves as a repository of relevant documents, public deliverables, and scientific publications, adding to the public results library in the [BATMACHINE community in Zenodo](#). The project partners actively support this task by sharing updates about publications, participation in conferences or new project results. The interested visitors can easily read through the content, download resources and get engaged via the newsletter form or social media links.

DBL is responsible for the design, realisation, maintenance, and update of both the website and the social network profiles. Both the structure and the external appearance of the website are developed considering the highest usability standards, ensuring a clear and easy navigation for all kinds of users and from all devices thanks to responsive design.

To ensure a secure, reliable, and dynamic website, a professional hosting service with a database service and backup features was chosen. The website was developed using the WordPress (www.wordpress.org) Content Management System (CMS), known for its reliability, extensive documentation support, and flexibility. Search Engine Optimization (SEO) functionalities have been enabled to enhance the website's visibility on major search engines.

To comply with the GDPR General Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament, the website adheres to well-known and secure services such as Iubenda (www.iubenda.com), with DBL acting as the data controller. Only necessary personal data voluntarily provided by users or collected automatically, such as cookies and navigation flows, are collected.

The list of blog post articles drafted by the partners and published on the News page of the website so far can be found in **Table 1**. The Consortium published twelve articles so far.

Figure 8: BATMACHINE News page

Table 1: List of BATMACHINE blog post articles

#	Title	Author
1	Sustainability in Cell Battery Production – Horizon Europe BATMACHINE Kick-off Meeting	DBL
2	Focus on EU industry primary advantage for battery manufacturing	VUB
3	The BATMACHINE website is up and running!	DBL
4	1° BATMACHINE General Assembly in Rome	DBL
5	The Future of Battery Slurry Mixing	SKZ/NFT
6	Improving Battery Manufacturing: Implementing Machine Interface Deployment Kits	SINTEF
7	Unlocking Power: The Calendering Step in Battery Manufacturing	FOM
8	Powering EU Battery Manufacturing – BATMACHINE 1st Press Release	DBL
9	2° BATMACHINE General Assembly in Basque Country	DBL
10	Countering Asian Dominance: Europe’s Road to Leadership in Battery Machinery Manufacturing	RWTH AACHEN
11	Sustainable energy storage: LFP battery Manufacturing and Integration with Renewables	POMEGA
12	Building a strong network for Sustainable Battery Manufacturing	DBL

The website performance is well established and has received so far 2.293 visitors since its launch on M4 (Sept.2023) gathering almost half of the visitors indicated by the Website Performance KPI (check Table 6) already by M18.

In Figure 9, Figure 10, and Figure 11, an overview website performance in terms of visitors and their behaviour, and visitors’ origin is provided.

Visits Overview

Figure 9: Website visitors' Overview

2,293 visits

Figure 10: Map of website visitor locations

1,676 visits (71.2%)

Figure 11: Map of website visitors' location (Europe)

As shown in Figure 7, the BATMACHINE website visitors come from all over the world. The visitors who visited the most the project website are from (in decreasing order):

- Germany
- Italy
- United States
- Turkey
- Belgium

2.2.2. Social Media networks

To disseminate the project outcomes effectively, the consortium opted to utilise mainstream social media platforms, including LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube. The mixed use of these channels facilitates engagement and awareness around the project topics, involving both the interested and key public, as well as a broader audience.

Periodic evaluations are conducted to assess the effectiveness of these dissemination channels and to monitor the achievement of the KPIs. This evaluation process enables a comprehensive understanding of the communication strategies, allowing the consortium to identify what is working well and what may require adjustment or improvement, to keep risks under control. By monitoring and analysing the impact of the communication efforts, BATMACHINE Consortium can refine its approach and optimise next steps towards the dissemination of the project outcomes.

The three social media were chosen with different aims.

- [LinkedIn](#), as a professional social network, attracts a group of interested professionals, stakeholders, policy makers and end-users that can exchange information and discuss about the project and its findings and new technologies. The information shared via LinkedIn is as informative as possible: thanks to the longer format that the platform allows, it is possible to discuss certain topics more extensively and create discussion in the comments section. Currently, the BATMACHINE LinkedIn page counts 324 followers, Below, Figure 12, Figure 13, and Figure 14 provide insights on the BATMACHINE LinkedIn page performance and activity in terms of audience engagement. Impressions peaked around M13 (June 2024), when the news on the BATMACHINE 2nd General Assembly in Bilbao was shared online. More specifically, Figure 14 provides an insight of the job functions of the BATMACHINE LinkedIn audience. The top three job categories are *Research, Business Development and Operations*, followed by *Engineering, Education and Program and Project Management* functions.

Figure 12: BATMACHINE LinkedIn page

Impressions

Organic 17,717

Figure 13: BATMACHINE LinkedIn page Impressions (reactions to posts)

Follower demographics
Job function

Show all →

Figure 14: Job function of the BATMACHINE audience

- **Twitter** (rebranded as X in July 2023) supports short and focused communication, so it will be used to promote news about the project (e.g., participation to events, deliverables released, etc...), relevant information and to interact with key actors for the project and sister projects news, giving the possibility to retweet their status in case it is strategic for BATMACHINE.

Due to the rebranding of the X social media platform, it is increasingly more difficult to reach the target audience that the project has envisioned to target through this platform. It is a phenomenon witnessed by many EU-funded projects. Moreover, linked with the rebranding of X, it is now necessary to establish a Premium+ account (at the cost of 8.54€ per month) to be able to use Analytics tools to examine the BATMACHINE X page performance. Thus, DBL has designed a mitigation strategy to cope with this issue. The mitigation action for this is to invest more effort in the project LinkedIn page, which is attracting the right audience and sees high levels of engagement from the followers. Also, as a further mitigation action, BATMACHINE established its [Bluesky profile](#), in order to reach the audience that was not possible to reach within X.

Figure 15: BATMACHINE Twitter/X page

- **YouTube** is a platform for publishing videos, enjoying them easily and free of charge. DBL's account will be used to publish BATMACHINE project video. A new account dedicated to BATMACHINE hasn't been created because the project will publish only a final video, so it would not be the most strategic option.

As the channels strongly differ from each other, they must be used in different ways. To ensure a successful communication, the project's tone of voice is slightly technical, but still friendly to a lay public. The attitude is plain but still authoritative, and informative. Using a clear and concise language to explain technical concepts and ideas ensures that the message more agile to take in. Scientific content is analysed and transformed into communicable content to be widely spread to the policy makers and relevant stakeholders and communities. Subtitles in English will be included when necessary to enable efficient video streaming in all possible environments.

2.2.3. Newsletter

A project e-newsletter is scheduled to be sent to partners, key stakeholders, specific audiences and interested contacts who have subscribed to the form on the website every six months. BATMACHINE will produce at least 5 issues of the project newsletter; each Newsletter issue is distributed during strategic periods close to important phases of the project, as well as project events and similar. The newsletter's aim is to keep the audience interested and informed about activities and results, public deliverables presentation, project progression, publications, with insights, useful links, and interesting readings.

For the delivery and management of contacts - including their privacy in compliance with the GDPR regulation (EU 2016/679) - a MailerLite account has been utilised. MailerLite (www.mailerlite.com) is a reliable and secure tool which guarantees transparent opt-in/opt-out choices to subscribers and supports a simple customizable design and effective delivery. To boost the number of subscribers, a [link to a subscription form](#) is available on the project's website homepage. Contacts are also collected during webinars, events and workshops, prior consent.

Below, Table 2 detailing the BATMACHINE Newsletter issues delivered so far and a link is provided for download on the dedicated resources page on the website.

Table 2: BATMACHINE Newsletter Issues

Issue N°	Delivered in	number of recipients
Newsletter #1	February 2024	63
Newsletter #2	July 2024	85
Newsletter #3	November 2024	96

2.2.4. Press Releases

Press releases serve as official statements targeted at members of the traditional news media to announce newsworthy content or results intended for promotion. A press release is a concise and captivating news story designed to capture the interest of journalists or publications.

During the duration of BATMACHINE, three press releases will be disseminated. The first was issued at the early stage of the project (M1-12), aiming to announce the project's concept, its goals, and distinctive features. This initial release aims to generate visibility and attract followers. The second press release will be distributed around halfway the project duration (M19-M22). The third and final press release will be published at the project's conclusion (M36-M42), summarising BATMACHINE's achievements in the field of smart batteries and new green technologies.

Whenever feasible, press releases are translated into the national languages of the consortium partners and distributed to press agencies in their respective countries, ensuring broader circulation of the information. All partners are requested to share their potential press contacts within their respective domains, networks, and geographic areas. The press releases have been disseminated online, in both English and the partners' local languages, to reach a wide range of audiences. This strategy aims to engage the largest possible number of individuals and maximise the project's impact.

The first BATMACHINE Press Release is [available on the project website resources page](#), translated in all the Consortium partners' languages. In the Table 3 below all mentions on partners' and external websites is provided.

Table 3: News about BATMACHINE published by external sources

Published	Language
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Neslihan Yuca Dođdu's project on the developing an optimized machinery with intelligent control processes for battery cell industrial manufacturing was entitled to receive support from EU Horizon project call.	EN
Europas nachhaltige Batteriezellenproduktion verbessern	DE
How batteries can become more sustainable	EN

2.2.5. Internal Communication

The internal communication strategy focuses on raising interaction and knowledge transfer between partners and ensure the success of the project. All partners interact regularly, and periodic updates are provided during planned General Assemblies and Executive Board meetings; additional meetings are organised when needed by the WP and task leaders to ensure fruitful and open exchange within the whole Consortium, as detailed in D1.1 (Project Implementation Plan).

Furthermore, the project makes use of several project management tools to maximise the effectiveness of internal communication and collaboration between partners, such as:

- The Cooperation Tool (CT5) is the main project management tool in BATMACHINE. CT5 is an integral solution enabling internal communication, financial reporting, the monitoring of needed actions, while being the document management system (DMS) to be used as a shared file repository for the consortium. In addition, VUB-hosted dedicated SharePoint is used to host living documents and collaborative work (e.g., deliverable drafting).
- SMTP mail exchange to help partners maintain effective collaboration, streamline information sharing, and foster a productive working relationship.
- Teleconferences and video conferences systems for periodic update meetings.
- Miro Boards to gather the ideas and track the proper execution of upcoming works.
- Mentimeter for online pooling while decision-making.

Efficacy, timeliness, and ease of interaction are the main objectives of this activity: any issues and inconveniences will be promptly addressed and solved to ensure continuity.

2.3. Dissemination Activities

The dissemination means and activities described in this section aim to enhance the outreach of project results and make scientific results a common good and maximise the project impact.

2.3.1. Dissemination towards the Advisory Board

Active contribution and participation from a set of stakeholders are key aspects for the achievement of BATMACHINE objectives. The consortium including partners and associated partners are supported by an effective and meaningful Advisory Board.

Ad-hoc meetings, consultations, and workshops (at least 3) are organised as in person or online meetings to collect Advisory Board members opinions and feedback, in collaboration with the scientific team and work package leaders. Moreover, the Advisory Board will be joining the project General Assemblies, when possible. In this regard, the Advisory Board members were invited and participated in a dedicated session during the [2nd General Assembly, held in Bilbao](#) in June 2024, hosted by TEKNIKER.

Figure 16: BATMACHINE Consortium at the 2nd GA in Bilbao

Figure 17: BATMACHINE Consortium at the 2nd GA in Bilbao

Furthermore, the Advisory Board members were invited to participate in the workshop held during the 3rd General Assembly, organised by RWTH Aachen in Braunschweig, in November 2024. Below, in Figure 18 and Figure 19, are reported some screenshots and pictures of the BATMACHINE Consortium and Advisory Board members during the 3rd General Assembly, which also included the 2nd Advisory Board meeting and the 1st BATMACHINE Workshop.

Figure 18: BATMACHINE Consortium and AB members at the 3rd General Assembly in Braunschweig (Nov.2024)

Figure 19: BATMACHINE Consortium and AB members at the 3rd General Assembly in Braunschweig (Nov.24/onsite)

2.3.2. Coordination, Networking and Synergies with other EU-funded and national initiatives

To ensure its success and visibility, the BATMACHINE project needs to collaborate and create synergies with other projects and initiatives in the Horizon Europe Programme framework, as well as with national projects. Collaborating with projects that have similar goals or are in the same field of research can be significant to its success. Sharing results and networking can help the project's growth, contribute to the research of sister projects in the field, create real synergies and explore the possibility of coordinating the dissemination activity or better organising the research.

Furthermore, BATMACHINE is part of the Battery Heroes 2.0 Cluster, a group of EU-funded dealing in energy storage and battery manufacturing. The Battery Heroes 2.0 Cluster, now counting 6 members, meets for regular monthly meetings, as well as involving the respective Consortiums in activities, such as workshops. Furthermore, the Cluster is also active in joint participation in conferences and relevant events, such as the [Transport Research Arena - TRA 2024](#) and the [Battery Innovation Days 2024](#). At both events, the Cluster joined with a booth showcasing the member projects.

The Battery Heroes 2.0 members are listed below in **Table 4**.

Table 4: List of Battery Heroes 2.0 Cluster members

Battery Heroes 2.0 Cluster	
BatWoMan	https://batwoman.eu/
Giga Green	https://gigagreenproject.eu/
greenSPEED	https://greenspeed-project.eu/
NoVOC	https://www.novoc.eu/
GigaBat	https://gigabat-project.eu/
BATMACHINE	https://batmachineproject.eu/

2.3.3. Third parties' Events and Conferences

All consortium members are committed to look for, take part in and/or attend both European and international networking conferences and domain-specific fairs and events, to disseminate BATMACHINE's advancements and results. The objective is to help raise awareness on the potential beneficial impacts of the project among a specialised audience and enlarge the pool of stakeholders.

As part of the scientific and industrial outreach, BATMACHINE actively looks for and participates in relevant conferences, exhibitions, and technical workshops. This helps the project in reaching key stakeholders and in establishing cooperation with the projects funded under the same topic and cluster. Furthermore, it allows BATMACHINE to contribute to the objectives of the Battery partnership to establish a world-leading sustainable and circular European battery value chain to drive transformation towards a carbon-neutral society.

A list of events and conferences in which BATMACHINE partners participated and presented the project can be found in **Table 5** below.

Table 5: List of Events and Conferences

Conference/event	Venue	When	Participation
Workshop on Batteries and Digitalisation (SINTEF internal workshop)	Trondheim, Norway	31.10.2023	Oral presentation of project overview
<u>The 24th International Nanotechnology Exhibition & Conference – Nano Tech 2024</u>	Tokyo, Japan	31.01-02.02.2024	BATMACHINE poster with project overview, featuring during partner presentation
<u>International Round Table on Materials Criticality – IRTC2024</u>	Turin, Italy	21-23/02/2024	Poster presentation
<u>CofBAT project final Event</u>	Brussels, Belgium	21.03.2024	Event participation
<u>Advanced Functional Material Congress 2024</u>	Stockholm, Sweden	25.03.2024	Shared project information to relevant stakeholders
<u>Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry – SETAC Europe 2024</u>	Seville, Spain	5-9.05.2024	Event participation
<u>Giga Europe 2024</u>	Stockholm, Sweden	12-13.03.2024	Shared project information to relevant stakeholders
<u>NATIONAL MATERIALS SCIENCE CONFERENCE</u>	Trondheim, Norway	28-29.08.2024	Event participation
<u>LOLABAT project Final Conference</u>	Milan, Italy	09.09.2024	Project overview presentation, participation in panel discussions as panelist
LiPLANET Sustainable Electrode/Cell Production Workshop	Braunschweig, Germany/online	19.09.2024	Event participation
<u>International Battery Production Conference – IBPC 2024</u>	Braunschweig, Germany	27-29.11.2024	Poster presentation (2), participation at session on

slurry mixing
as speaker

2.3.4. Scientific Articles and Papers

During the lifetime of the project, BATMACHINE will produce at least 15 (fifteen) scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals. BATMACHINE consortium is committed to Open Access Publishing. Each partner must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to the project results.

This refers to providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user:

1. As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.
2. Ensure immediate open access to the deposited publication via the repository. At the beginning of the project, the consortium set up a repository (i.e., a dedicated [BATMACHINE community in Zenodo](#), developed under the European OpenAire programme) for publications derived from the project following the green open access principle.
3. Ensure open access, via the repository, to the bibliographic metadata.

To ensure a high visibility for the scientific papers and articles, following the guidelines presented by Springer in the article "[Maximize your visibility. Promoting your research effectively](#)" is recommended. This process increases the visibility and impact of the research, as it is more likely to be cited and referenced by other researchers.

BATMACHINE follows the European guidelines on the large-scale accessibility of project findings. Open access publishing is granted to all scientific publications resulting from the project. However, all articles derived from BATMACHINE are also available on the project website and the project community in Zenodo. **Table 6** provides a prospective list of potential domain-related scientific journals collected with the support of all partners.

At the time of this report, a scientific paper is in preparation from VUB related to the research in WP5 – *Energy, Cost, and Sustainability Assessment*.

Table 6: List of Scientific Journals

Scientific peer-reviewed journals	Peer reviewed
International, transdisciplinary journal focusing on Cleaner Production, Environmental, and Sustainability research and practice.	Yes, Open Access
International, transdisciplinary journal focusing on cleaner ways of sourcing, transforming, transporting, delivering, and using energy.	Yes, Open Access

Journal on the science, technology and applications of sources of electrochemical power, science and applications of primary and secondary batteries, fuel cells, supercapacitors and photo-electrochemical cells.	Journal of Power Sources https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-power-sources	Yes, Open Access
interdisciplinary journal publishing original research covering aspects of materials, engineering, chemistry, physics, and biology relevant to sustainable applications in energy conversion and storage.	ACS Applied Energy Materials https://pubs.acs.org/journal/aaemcq	Yes, Open Access
International Journal on the Science and Technology of Wet and Dry Particulate Systems.	Powder Technology https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/powder-technology	Yes, Open Access
Peer-reviewed journal that covers all aspects of chemical engineering, process engineering, biotechnology, and design of apparatus.	Chemie Ingenieur Technik https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/15222640	Yes, Open Access
The Journal focuses on all aspects of energy storage, in particular systems integration, electric grid integration, modelling and analysis, novel energy storage technologies, sizing and management strategies, business models for operation of storage systems and energy storage developments worldwide.	Journal of Energy Storage https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-energy-storage	Yes, Open Access

3. Monitoring Impact and KPI definition

Monitoring a range of dissemination activities is crucial for achieving success and maximising the impact of the communication strategy employed by the BATMACHINE project. By closely monitoring the communication campaign, the project can evaluate the effectiveness of its messages, make necessary adjustments based on real-time feedback, and ultimately accomplish its communication objectives. Furthermore, monitoring the communication activities helps identify areas for improvement, paving the way for the next advancements.

Several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been identified to track the progress of the dissemination efforts. **Table 7** provides a comprehensive list of all the dissemination and communication KPIs identified for the BATMACHINE project.

Table 7: BATMACHINE Communication & Dissemination KPIs

Tool/Channel	Objective	Target Audience	KPI	Status at M18
Project Website	Provide a public online showcase of the project, including an overview of the project, up-to-date information on project results, public reports and papers; project events, etc.	All targets	Unique Visitors (based on Analytics): 5000	2562 visitors
Promotional material (brochure, roll-up, visual identity)	Create awareness and also exploit viral marketing effects	All targets	Visual Identity	1 classic flyer, 1 horizontal brochure, 1 rollup
Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube)	Create interest around the project and involve relevant stakeholders in the project	T1, T2, T4, T6	300 LinkedIn contacts 300 Twitter followers	324 LinkedIn followers, 86 Twitter/X followers
Press media and newsletter	Raise awareness on the project Results	Press media: All targets Newsletter: T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6	3 press releases 5 newsletters online	1 press release translated in 9 languages
Participation in conferences	Spread project results among the scientific community	Mainly T6	20 conferences (10 presenting and 10 attending) 8 exhibition/fair where industrial equipment is presented	11 conferences and events (5 presenting (posters), 6 attending)
Scientific publications	Spread project results among the scientific community	Mainly T6	15 papers	1 in preparation

Public and engagement driven events	Contribute to building and strengthening the community of stakeholders	Dissemination Events: All targets Thematic Workshops: T1, T2, T3, T4, T5	2 dissemination events (>200 participants) 3 thematic workshops (>200 participants) 4 panels/workshops specific guidelines on how to scale up a battery production line up to a Gigafactory	BATMACHINE Launch Event in June 2025 around the same dates of BEPA General Assembly 1 thematic workshop titled “ <i>Cell production in Europe – Market-related aspects and innovation</i> ” on 26.11.2024
Networks and synergies with relevant projects/initiatives	Provide continued visibility, permanent networking and a channel to reach stakeholders	T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6	10 synergies/joint actions	5 related projects in the Battery Heroes Cluster 1 working group on LCA and sustainability assessment (within Battery Heroes)

These measures can be refined, updated, and integrated during the project lifecycle, according to the needs that may be encountered along the way.

4. Interaction with other tasks

This deliverable is directly linked to Task T7.1 - *Communication and Dissemination strategy* and Task T7.2 - *Communication and Dissemination activities*. These tasks last for the whole duration of the BATMACHINE project. Moreover, this deliverable is strictly linked to Task T7.3 - *Stakeholders’ collaboration framework and engagement*, and Task T7.4 - *Exploitation*. Nevertheless, WP7 - Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Collaboration is linked to all other Work Packages, as it is related to all the other tasks in the project, since it aims at spreading the project main findings and outputs throughout the project implementation.

The Exploitation activities are defined and listed in the related deliverable D7.3 – *Exploitation Plan (a)*, delivered at M6.

Finally, the overall Communication and Dissemination strategy follows the Data Management Plan indications and is compliant of the rules regarding the production and usage of project outputs when organising and managing the BATMACHINE communication and dissemination.

5. Conclusion

This report details the activities and progress done within the WP7 – Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Collaboration from the beginning of the project until M18. In the document, the actions are reported and detailed by single item. For a more comprehensive and specific view on the project Communication and Dissemination strategy, please refer to D7.1 – *Communication and Dissemination Plan (a)*.

This deliverable will be updated in Deliverable D7.6 – *Final Report on Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination and Stakeholders' engagement activities*, due for M42, at the end of the project.

6. Deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

7. References

- BATMACHINE - D7.1 – *Communication and Dissemination plan (a)* - <https://zenodo.org/records/12685099>